

Addressing the Professional Development Needs of Adult Numeracy Practitioners in Ireland

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The development of a numerate society is an international and national priority in education. Given such importance, there is a need for increased attention on adult education, and particularly to the availability and quality of adult numeracy education. While there has been considerable focus on mathematics teaching in general, there is a dearth of research and resources in relation to teaching adult numeracy. Consequently, there is an unmet demand for the professional development of adult numeracy practitioners with many looking for opportunities to network and further develop their practice. This study aimed to design, implement, and evaluate a professional development model that supported adult numeracy practitioners in developing the necessary skills to support their students. After an initial needs analysis, a series of six online ‘Numeracy-Meets’ were designed and implemented between February and May 2022. After all the Numeracy-Meets had taken place, five practitioners took part in individual semi-structured interviews to evaluate their experiences. This paper details the design, implementation, and evaluation of these Numeracy-Meets.

Keywords: adult numeracy, practitioners, professional development, Numeracy-Meets

Background to the Study

It is well documented that numeracy skills are critically important for the adult population to support active citizenship in the economic, social, and community spheres (Goos et al., 2023). However, despite such recognised importance, findings from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Programme’s for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), suggest that large numbers of adults have low or very low numeracy skills (OECD, 2019). The PIAAC numeracy proficiency scale is divided into six proficiency levels: Levels 1 to 5 and below Level 1. When Ireland took part in PIAAC (2012), it was found that over one-quarter (25.3%) of adults scored at or below Level 1 on the numeracy scale (OECD, 2013). This score ranked Ireland 19th out of 24 participating countries and suggested that 754,000 Irish people struggle with everyday numeracy (NALA, 2017). This concerning issue has been reflected in a continued national policy focus over the past decade which has culminated in the publication of the first Adult Literacy for Life (ALL) Strategy for Ireland in 2021. This cross-Government strategy is underpinned by one simple vision: “An Ireland where every adult has the necessary literacy, numeracy and digital literacy to fully engage in society and realise their potential” (Government of Ireland, 2021, p.33).

In Ireland, the Education and Training Boards (ETBs) are the national providers of post-compulsory Further Education and Training (FET), alongside a smaller range of adult and community education groups. ETBs offer a range of accredited and unaccredited courses of learning, and they have responsibility for providing adult education and training, and youth work programmes in Ireland. In terms of adult numeracy education, the provision across this

sector remains diverse and little is known about the delivery of courses, those who attend them, and those who teach on them. For example, the National Adult Literacy Agency (NALA) estimate that there are currently over 40,000 adults attending literacy courses mainly provided by the ETB Adult Literacy Service in Ireland (NALA, 2023). However, because adult numeracy is considered to be a component of adult literacy, there is no data available to ascertain how many adults access or persist with numeracy-specific provision (Goos et al., 2023). In 2021, SOLAS (a State agency of the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science) commissioned a research study that sought to “...capture and document standalone and integrated adult numeracy activity in the Education and Training Board (ETB) context, in order to develop good practice guidelines and inform future development of adult numeracy policy and practice” (SOLAS, 2021, p. 6). It was envisaged that such an endeavour would provide a contemporary overview of numeracy provision in Ireland and inform a series of guidelines that would help shape the future of numeracy provision for adults. There were four main guidelines set out by SOLAS, the last of which focused on ‘Supporting and developing adult numeracy tutors’. This fourth guideline proposed that ETBs “Plan for adult numeracy tutors’ professional development” and “Create networking opportunities for adult numeracy tutors” (SOLAS, 2021, p. 11). With these recommendations in mind, this study¹ sought to address the following research question: How can the needs of adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland be addressed through the design, implementation, and evaluation of a professional development model?

The Study

The research team for this study brought together expertise in the field of numeracy, teacher education, and adult numeracy education. The researchers had worked together on previous adult numeracy projects and felt well placed in targeting Guideline 4 of the SOLAS (2021) report. They also sought the support of NALA which is an independent charity committed to supporting people with literacy and numeracy difficulties in Ireland. Since its establishment in 1980, NALA has developed and delivered professional development resources and opportunities for adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland. The researchers felt that the organisation’s knowledge and networks in the area would be an invaluable addition to the project team.

Ethical approval for the study was granted in January 2022 by the Social Research Ethics Committee in University College Cork (Log 2021-226). The research was carried out in three main phases which took place over a five-month period between February and June 2022. Phase 1 was a needs analysis of a sample of adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland and the subsequent design of a professional development model. This model was implemented and evaluated in Phase 2 and Phase 3, respectively. The write up of this paper will be structured using each of these sequential Phases to guide the reader through the study.

¹ This paper is based on Prendergast, M., Forester, A., O’Meara, N., O’Sullivan, K., and Faulkner, F. (2023). Numeracy-Meets: An innovative professional development model for adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland. *Irish Educational Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2023.2209854>

Phase 1 – The Design

The first phase of the research was a needs analysis of a sample of adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland. This was done through an online questionnaire using an instrument adapted from the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) 2018 Teacher Questionnaire Professional Development section. There were three parts to the questionnaire, namely:

1. Background information
2. Attitude towards and perception of teaching
3. Professional development needs.

The 16-item questionnaire was circulated via a Microsoft Forms link using non-probability sampling through NALA adult numeracy networks in February 2022. It was completed by 33 respondents. The quantitative data was recorded and transferred into an SPSS (version 25) file for statistical analysis. The data from any open-ended questions were transcribed into a Microsoft Word for content analysis in relation to the professional development needs of adult numeracy practitioners. Respondents ranged in age from 30 – 69 and the majority were female (79%). Prendergast et al. (2023) provide a detailed description of the analysis of the data. In summary, in terms of professional development, 87% had engaged in online courses or seminars in the previous 12 months. However, they identified specific areas in which they had a need for Continuous Professional Development (CPD). For example, 65% of practitioners indicated that they had a moderate to high level of need for CPD in pedagogical competencies in teaching numeracy. Furthermore, 75% of practitioners revealed a moderate to high level of need for CPD in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills for teaching numeracy. In an open-ended question on how the CPD needs of adult numeracy practitioners might be best supported, the main findings were centred on workshops, communities of practice, or collective forums where ideas could be shared. Participants also noted that shorter inputs which did not involve a long commitment would be most suitable.

Taking the findings from the needs analysis into account, the research team decided to design a series of online Numeracy-Meets “to best address practitioners' needs”. The term Numeracy-Meets was adapted from the Teach-Meet model of professional development which has been referred to as ‘guerrilla CPD’ (Bennett, 2012). According to Blanchett (2014), Teach-Meets “provide a nice informal atmosphere to share ideas and good practice with a chance for everyone to have their say” (p. 5). Many consider Teach-Meets to be based on the community of practice (CoP) model of CPD (Amond et al., 2018). According to Wenger (1998), it is necessary to consider three defining characteristics in order for a CoP to emerge: a focus on a shared interest and domain; involvement in joint activities, discussions and sharing of information; and the development of a shared repertoire of resources. After considering each of these characteristics, the authors were satisfied that the Numeracy-Meets model would meet the criteria of a CoP. The shared focus would be adult numeracy; there would be discussions of practice and sharing of planning and instructional approaches; and there would be a shared repertoire of resources gathered after each Numeracy-Meet.

Given the dispersed nature of numeracy practitioners in Ireland, the Numeracy-Meets needed to be a nationwide professional development strategy for remote practitioners to network and further develop their practice. According to Wenger et al. (2002), CoPs can exist both physically and virtually. Karam et al. (2018) noted that online CoPs afford promising alternatives for overcoming the absence of collocated peers and so it was decided that the Numeracy-Meets would take place virtually.

With all of this in mind, six online Numeracy-Meets were designed with the aim of providing practitioners with professional development in which learning could occur in an informal way, primarily through social interaction.

Phase 2 – Implementation

In terms of structure, the underlying theory of each Numeracy-Meet was an adaptation from Farley-Ripple and Buttram’s (2014) work on developing learning communities in the United States (see Figure 1). The central assumption of any community is that collaboration helps and that teaching and learning is more effective if practice and experiences are openly shared and discussed (Bolisani et al., 2020). Thus, there were three important components to the planned structure of each Numeracy-Meet. As evidenced from Figure 1, analysis of evidence, discussion about teaching practice, and instructional planning were at the heart of effective collaboration between the numeracy practitioners.

Figure 1

Underlying Theory of Each Numeracy-Meet

The content focus of the Numeracy-Meets centred on specific life domains (e.g., financial, health, digital, etc) and related uses and practices of numeracy in the context of work, family, and everyday life. The common format of each Meet generally involved a twenty-minute input on a specified topic from an invited speaker followed by discussion and contributions from several attending practitioners. The resources from each of the Numeracy-

Meets were shared with all participants and are available at <https://epistem.ie/numeracy-meets/>.

As evidenced in Figure 2, the implementation of the six Numeracy-Meets took place between 16th of February 2022 and 11th of May 2022. They were facilitated online using the Microsoft Teams platform and were scheduled on Wednesdays between 1pm and 2pm. Practitioners were asked to register their interest to attend the Numeracy-Meets via a Microsoft Forms link which was circulated through NALA's adult numeracy networks.

Figure 2

Marketing Poster with Overview of the Numeracy-Meets

In total, 60 adult numeracy practitioners registered their interest. There was a wide range of diversity in the background of the practitioners who registered. For example, 14 of the 16 ETBs in Ireland were represented, along with adult numeracy practitioners from the Irish Prison Service, third level, and other non-profit organisations. There was a range of 14–23 attendees across the six Meets and the median number of attendees who attended each Meet was 20. Of the 60 adult numeracy practitioners who initially registered their interest, 40 attended at least one of the Numeracy-Meets. There was a core group of 15 practitioners who attended at least four of the six Numeracy-Meets.

Phase 3 – Evaluation

The third and final phase concerns the evaluation of the Numeracy-Meets model. The data with which to evaluate the intervention was gathered using semi-structured interviews. After the six Numeracy-Meets had taken place, five participants (pseudonyms used - Abbi, Brian, Chloe, Deirdre, and Eimear) were purposively selected from the core group of 15 practitioners who had attended at least four of the six Numeracy-Meets. These five participants were purposively selected to ensure that there was a proportional gender balance (one male and four female practitioners) and that there was representation from five different

ETB's and adult education settings. Once selected, an email invitation was sent to take part in a one-to-one interview to evaluate their experience of the Numeracy-Meets. This email contained an information sheet explaining the key points and procedures of the study. All five participants consented to take part and the interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams in June 2022. The interviews were semi-structured, with questions divided around three main areas, namely participants' perceptions of Numeracy Meets, the effectiveness of the CPD, and the future sustainability of the model. The data from each interview was transcribed into a Microsoft Word document and content analysis was performed by two of the authors. The application of content analysis ensured a systematic examination and interpretation of the qualitative data which informed our overall findings.

Overall, the data from the interviews indicated that practitioners found the intervention useful and felt that the sessions positively affected their practice. Interviewees liked the combination of theory and practice and the mutual sharing of practical ideas which took place at the Numeracy-Meets.

Deirdre: I found it very good. It went through theory and then it related back to our everyday practices. It went back over past research that had been done and applied it and probably showed where it was going for the future.

Practitioners were asked about their overall perception of Numeracy-Meets as a professional development model, in terms of what they most and least liked. All participants contended that the Numeracy-Meets provided relevant content, useful ideas for the classroom, and insightful information. They enjoyed the participation of invited speakers from different areas and the adult education focus. Chloe noted that she would share the research findings discussed at Numeracy-Meets with coordinators at her education centre so that the research could inform decision making at the centre.

Chloe: The resources that were made available as well the presentations and the recordings I think they are a great tool for us maths tutors to have to try to influence strategy at centre level if we can.

On the other hand, participants suggested that further practitioner participation in Numeracy-Meets sessions would be desirable.

Abbi: I would like to see even more tutors. I know every day we had tutors give a talk you know. I think I'd like to see that maybe, more of that...

They contended that more opportunities for discussion would have been beneficial and would have provided participants with further chances to interact with each other and be honest about the challenges they face.

In terms of structure, all interviewees liked the flexibility of the one-hour Numeracy-Meets sessions, which were conducted online via Microsoft Teams. In comparison to one-day, face-to face CPD sessions, Numeracy-Meets were short and continuous, giving practitioners time to absorb what they learned.

Deirdre: It was nice and condensed. I liked the topics. I liked the way it was run. You got a little bit of everything in a short period of time.

Abbi felt that online CPD was easier than face-to-face sessions, which are time-consuming and expensive due to travel and childcare costs. Deirdre concurred that face-to-face CPD is time-consuming and requires the practitioner to travel but noted that it does provide opportunities for practitioners to engage in informal chats to share ideas. Overall, all interviewees agreed that Numeracy-Meets were a very good model of CPD and expressed a desire for them to continue in the future.

Abbi: The only suggestion would be to continue having similar meetings as they were great support for those of us working in adult numeracy. It can sometimes feel that the issues we encountered are unique to our situation when in fact it's very similar in all adult education areas.

Conclusion

Given the vision of the ALL Strategy, the research outlined in this study is timely and topical and provides useful insights into the professional development needs and wants of adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland. The short implementation and evaluation of the model suggests that the Numeracy-Meets provided an effective, flexible, and cost-effective model for supporting and developing adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland. The participants developed a sense of being part of a larger community with a common goal to improve adult numeracy provision. However, despite the positive feedback, the authors are also aware that there is still much work to be done for Numeracy-Meets to become a sustainable professional development model going forward. While there was huge enthusiasm amongst the core participants for the series to continue, the longer-term viability and wider scale needs to be considered and this is more difficult in adult education in Ireland given the diverse and dispersed nature of practitioners. Going forward, further research is needed to create a solid foundation for practical interventions which support the development of adult numeracy practitioners in Ireland. However, Numeracy-Meets offer a useful starting point for the establishment of a national adult numeracy learning community to support practitioners in sharing resources and local good practice. They also provide a basis for the design, implementation, and evaluation of future research-informed professional development to support adult practitioners.

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